

Experimental investigation of fracture mechanism in organically modified silica-based coating applied on austenitic stainless steel AISI 904L under monotonic and very high cycle fatigue loading

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Organic–inorganic sol–gel coating
Austenitic stainless steel
Monotonic loading
Fatigue
Fracture

ABSTRACT

Surface morphology significantly influences the fatigue life of the metallic materials. Therefore, improving surface performance is important for economic and safety applications. Silica-based coatings are anticipated to protect the metallic materials under synergistic operating conditions, such as fatigue and corrosion. However, pure inorganic silica-based coatings are brittle and fail to protect metallic materials. The properties of the sol–gel coatings can be determined by optimizing synthesis factors, such as synthesis steps, precursors, solvents, and catalysts. Organically modified silica-based sol–gel coatings were synthesized using 3-glycidoxypropyl trimethoxysilane and 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane as precursors, with ethanol as the solvent. The resulting coating was named EtOH. This coating was applied on the surface of stable austenitic stainless steel AISI 904L with the dip coating method. The fracture behavior of the coating during monotonic loading has been studied by interrupted tensile tests at different load steps and examined closely with scanning electron microscopy. On the other hand, very high cycle fatigue experiments were conducted using an ultrasonic fatigue testing system at load frequency of 20 kHz on coated specimens to investigate the fracture behavior of the coating during cyclic loading. Three different kinds of fracture due to stress relaxation in the coating and at its interface with substrate were observed in monotonic loading. The same kinds of stress relaxation were observed in cyclic loading with the difference being that the range of experienced elongation in cyclic tests was significantly smaller. Therefore, the fracture in cyclic loading were concentrated in the vicinity of macro crack. The application of organically modified coatings could suppress the persistent slip bands and result in increased fatigue life for coated specimens.

1. Introduction

The sol–gel method enables the production of various materials with different functionalities. The broad applicability of the sol–gel method in generating a diverse range of products is facilitated using precursors containing non-hydrolysable moieties, catalysts, synthesis solvents, and stabilization conditions [1–5]. In case of protective coatings, designed to withstand synergic conditions such as corrosive environments and mechanical stresses, enhancing mechanical properties stands as a key factor. Presently, modifying oxide matrices with nanopowders has become a prevalent method for improving specific mechanical factors. This modification process enhances the coating's hardness and resistance to cracking and chipping [6], erosion damage [6,7], tribological

characteristics [8], resilience to elastic deformation [6], Young's modulus [6,7], and reduction in brittleness [6]. The mechanical properties of sol–gel coatings are determined by their structure, which is controlled during the synthesis step. Coatings with denser and more compact network structures exhibit greater resistance to mechanical stresses [9]. The degree of crosslinking in sol–gel films significantly impacts adhesion strength and the response to normal and shear stresses acting at the crack [10]. According to literature findings, partial solvent evaporation during the synthesis process can result in increased porosity, leading to a decrease in scratch resistance and hardness [9]. The thickness of the sol–gel coatings is of importance. Thin adhesive films reduce in-plane shrinkage, residual and strain tensile stresses, while high thicknesses of sol–gel films can generate delamination and failure at the interface [11].

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2024.104536>

Received 4 March 2024; Received in revised form 6 June 2024; Accepted 11 June 2024

Available online 15 June 2024

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Nomenclature			
EBSD	electron backscatter diffraction	k	linear elastic stress-elongation factor
FEM	finite element method	N	number of cycles
FIB	focused ion beam	N_f	number of cycles to failure
SEM	scanning electron microscopy	R	radius
USFT	ultrasonic fatigue testing	$R_{p0.2}$	0.2 % yield strength
VHCF	very high cycle fatigue	R_z	maximum peak-to-valley height of the profile
C	coated specimen	S_a	oscillation amplitude
CS	cross section	t	time
E	Young's modulus	T	temperature
HM	Martens hardness	U	uncoated specimen
HV10	Vicker's hardness	wt%	weight percent
IR	infrared	\varnothing	diameter
		σ_a	stress amplitude
		σ_{UTS}	ultimate tensile strength

Fig. 1. Detailed view of VHCF specimen fastened in USFT (a) oscillation value measured by laser vibrometer (b) and recalculated mechanical stresses as well as development of temperature within the specimen during one load pulse (c).

Number of investigations have been done to study the monotonic [12] and cyclic behavior [11] of sol-gel coatings. Fatigue properties of inorganic ceramic thin films, demonstrating their exceptional durability up to the high cycle fatigue range of 10^7 cycles [11]. Other investigations on hybrid organic-inorganic sol-gel coatings show that the incorporation of organic moieties into the inorganic structure of sol-gel enhances flexibility, thereby influencing fatigue behavior [13]. This study is focused on investigation of fracture mechanism of hybrid organic-inorganic sol-gel coating in monotonic loading and compare the results with fracture at the cyclic loading.

2. Experimental methods and materials

2.1. Tensile loading

Tensile coated specimen underwent loading at various levels, with its condition examined at the identical position using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The initial focused ion beam (FIB)-cut position served as a reference marker, facilitating the precise relocation of the same position within the material during the interrupted tensile loading test. All the FIB-cut and SEM observation have been done with Tescan Gaia III. The interrupted tensile test was conducted to investigate the fracture mechanism of the coating under monotonic loading conditions. Employing the advanced tensile/compression module by Kmmrath Weiss GmbH, capable of applying forces up to 5000 N, the study began by subjecting an uncoated specimen to loading until failure with

displacement rate of $0.5 \mu\text{m/s}$.

2.2. Cyclic loading

The very high cycle fatigue (VHCF) tests were conducted using an ultrasonic fatigue testing (USFT) system developed at the Institute of Materials Science and Engineering of the RPTU in Kaiserslautern. This USFT is capable of operating at a load frequency of 20 kHz (Fig. 1a).

The tests in this study were carried out in room temperature. At high frequencies, the specimens will experience self heating. To monitor and control the temperature, an infrared (IR) radiation pyrometer was employed. Maintaining the ambient room temperature was achieved through a pulse-pause test method, where compressed air flow was simultaneously applied to the specimen [14–17]. The details about performance and principle of VHCF experiments for austenitic stainless steels can be found in [14]. The experiments could not be performed in force control mode, due to inability to measure force in USFT system. However, the precise measurement of specimen oscillation using a laser vibrometer has enabled the experiments to be conducted in displacement control mode [14]. In Fig. 1b the plot illustrates the oscillation value versus time for one pulse. Fig. 1c presents the recalculated amount of stress in the center of specimen at the same pulse time accompanied by a temperature development within the specimen. Calculation of stress is done indirectly using the finite element method (FEM). For stress calculations, a steady-state analysis is performed using Abaqus FEM software. During this process, the linear relationship

Fig. 2. Grain orientation map of initial state of AISI 904L (a), the condensed structural formula of organically modified silica-based sol-gel coating (b).

Table 1

Chemical composition of AISI 904L in wt%.

C	Cr	Ni	N	Nb	Mo	Si	Cu	Ti	P	Si
0.026	19.92	24.34	0.057	0.03	4.22	0.55	1.42	0.02	0.017	<0.001

Table 2

Mechanical properties and density of AISI 904L as well as Young’s modulus, hardness of base material and the coating.

$R_{p0.2}$ AISI 904 L (MPa)	σ_{UTS} AISI 904 L (MPa)	Density AISI 904 L (kg/m ³)	Poisson’s ratio AISI 904 L	E AISI 904 L (GPa)	HM AISI 904 L (MPa)	HV10	E coating (GPa)	HM coating (MPa)
307	631	7854	0.3	187	1814 ± 49	149.3 ± 1.5	2.44	159 ± 15

between oscillation amplitude and stress at the middle of the specimen is evaluated. This analysis establishes a material and design specific parameter called k factor. In this case of study, the k factor is determined to be 23.56 MPa/μm.

2.3. Base material and coating

In this study specimens from austenitic stainless steel AISI 904L (X1NiCrMoCu25205) as base material were coated with the organically

modified silica-based sol-gel using dip coating method. By using a Vickers indenter on a Zwick/Roell ZHU250 tabletop device HV10 was determined for AISI 904L. On the other hand, the microhardness measurements for the austenitic stainless steel AISI 904L were conducted through FISCHERSCOPE® HM2000 with the load force of 1 N. Additionally, for precise information regarding the coating, nano indentation was employed using Micro Combi Tester (MCT), CSM Instrument, with a pyramidal Berkovich tip and maximum force of 0.1 mN as explained in [18].

Fig. 3. Geometry of specimens for tensile tests (a), and VHCF tests (b), with dimensions provided in millimeters.

Fig. 4. FIB-cut cross section observation of coated flat tensile specimen (a) and coated VHCF specimen (b) at initial state.

Prior to coating, the base material underwent ultrasonic cleaning in an acetone bath followed by an acid treatment with 0.15 % HNO_3 in ethanol (96 %, POCH, Gliwice, Poland) as described in [2]. The coatings were prepared using (3-glycidioxypropyl) trimethoxysilane (97 % purity, GPTMS, Alfa Aesar, Kandel, Germany) and 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (98 % purity, APTES, Alfa Aesar, Kandel, Germany) as precursors, with ethanol (96 %, POCH, Gliwice, Poland) serving as the reaction environment and HNO_3 (65 %, POCH, Gliwice, Poland) as the catalyst. The molar ratio of GPTMS to APTES was 1:1, and the volume ratio of precursors to ethanol to catalyst was 1:2:0.01. The synthesis was conducted with magnetic stirring for 2 h at room temperature (21 ± 1 °C). Subsequently, the coating was stabilized at 180 °C for 3 h with a temperature gradient of 0.5 °C/min using a laboratory dryer (POL-EOKO-APARATURA SP.J., SL 53 STD, Wodzisław Śląski, Poland). The microstructure of the AISI 904L is illustrated by electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) analysis through a longitudinal cross-section (Fig. 2a). The material exhibits a homogeneous austenitic microstructure with solution annealing twins. The organic component of the coating comprises substantial amine and alcohol groups linked to the silica molecules with the structural formula shown in Fig. 2b and the chemical composition of austenitic stainless steel AISI 904L is given in Table 1. Table 2 summarizes the tensile properties, density, and hardness of base material, as well as the hardness and elastic modulus of the coating as indicated by nano indentation.

2.4. Specimen geometry

The coating was applied to a flat tensile specimen (Fig. 3a) for tensile loading and to VHCF specimen (Fig. 3b) for fatigue loading. The modal frequency analysis of this specimen design was run to ensure the specimen eigenfrequency lay within the working frequency range of the ultrasonic testing fatigue machine [19]. Flat tensile specimens were produced using electrical discharge machining from the base material rod. Subsequently, they underwent mechanical polishing up to a maximum peak-to-valley height of the profile, within a single sampling length of $R_z = 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. For the production of VHCF specimens, a turning process was employed. Post-turning, the specimens underwent additional polishing to achieve a polished surface with an $R_z = 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. The uncoated specimens' surfaces' roughness was examined using a Nano-Focus Focal Microscope by examining three distinct positions.

To ensure the continuity and appearance of the coating in cross-section, a FIB-cut was performed on the coated flat specimen (Fig. 4a) and coated VHCF specimen (Fig. 4b), where the coating had a thickness of 270 nm and 500 nm respectively. Determining the exact thickness of the coating is a challenging task depending on different variables such as

Fig. 5. Nominal stress / load force versus elongation diagram of tensile test.

rate of dipping, composition, and rate of pulling, and aging time. However, keeping the coating thickness in sub-micron values was the aim of this project.

Examining the cross-section of the base material showed a pronounced distinction between the flat tensile specimen and the VHCF specimen. The VHCF specimen exhibited the presence of a nanocrystalline layer, accompanied by a linear pattern beneath the surface. This feature is attributed to the turning production method employed for the VHCF specimen. Conversely, the nanocrystalline layer in the flat specimen, produced through electrical discharge machining and subsequent mechanical polishing, was notably thin and almost negligible in comparison.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Tensile loading

To analyze the cracking and fracture behavior within the coating during monotonic loading, an interrupted tensile test was conducted. The resulting load versus elongation diagram is depicted in Fig. 5. Additionally, for enhanced comprehension, the nominal stress in the middle of the specimen is represented. After SEM analysis of the initial surface state (Fig. 6a, c), the specimen was loaded up to 360 MPa /1700 N (step 1). The 1st step was chosen within the macroscopic elastic regime of AISI 904L. Subsequently, the observation of the specimen was conducted in its unloaded state. Fig. 6b and d show the change of the specimen's surface after loading. Despite the stress of the 1st step being

Fig. 6. SEM observation of the coated tensile specimen at initial state (a), (c), and after loading until 360 MPa / 1700 N (b), (d).

chosen in the macroscopic elastic regime, few slip bands were clearly visible on the specimen surface (Fig. 6d). These slip bands were distinct from the surface's micro-scale topography after mechanical polishing. Observations at this step showed that the coating remained firmly adhered to the steel, with no micro-crack initiation over the slip bands. Given that the elastic modulus of coating, which is about 77 times smaller than that of steel (see Tab. 2), the coating experienced a smaller stress amplitude for the same elongation. Consequently, the stress developed in the coating during loading and subsequently locally within the coating due to the emergence of slip bands, remained in the elastic regime for the coating.

The 2nd and 3rd load steps were until 445 MPa / 2100 N and 509 MPa / 2400 N, respectively. Both steps were in the elastic–plastic regime of the AISI 904L, resulting in plastic specimen elongation of 92 μm and 300 μm. Due to the specimen's geometry, no strain measurements and calculations were performed. Fig. 7 compares the changes in the specimen's surface between these two load steps. Upon reviewing the overall images and pictures in higher magnification, three kinds of fractures appeared in the coating: delamination accompanied by short micro-cracks, and two variations of long interconnected micro-cracks. At the 2nd step, the number of delamination sites was limited (Fig. 7a), and the length of these types of micro-cracks was relatively short, as seen in Fig. 7c, where the micro-cracks are locked between solution annealing twins. Therefore, the 2nd step or shortly before that was the onset of delamination. Fig. 7e reveals two additional types of interconnected

micro-cracks, which consisted of firstly, micro-cracks with the opening of 50–150 nm, and secondly, the micro-cracks with an opening of about 30 nm. According to the tensile stress relaxation in the coating and coating/substrate interface studied by Atkinson et al. [20], the latter is formed by elastic relaxation when the depth of the crack is not yet through the thickness of the coating, and the former is due to plastic relaxation, formed by sliding of the coating at the interface of the micro-crack without delamination. Henceforth, these micro-cracks will be referred to as elastic and sliding cracks, respectively. Following an increase in load during the 3rd step, the opening of these elastic cracks expanded, transforming them into sliding cracks (see Fig. 7f). In the 3rd step, in addition to expanding the previously existing micro-cracks, a considerable number of delamination sites with different lengths appeared (Fig. 7b). Upon reviewing Fig. 7b, it can be concluded that micro-cracks are perpendicular to the loading direction; however, the slip direction varies according to the specific grain orientation. Additionally, micro-cracking in the coating was less pronounced in specific grains, particularly in regions where plastic deformation was less (Fig. 7e, f). In conclusion, increasing the load from the 2nd step to the 3rd step resulted in a significant increase in the quantity and length and opening of micro-cracks. The initiation of microcracks was observed in locations distinct from the FIB-cut, indicating that the FIB-cut notch with width of 15 μm and depth of 10 μm was inadequate to initiate cracks under monotonic loading conditions. This observation highlights that fracture emergence is predominantly influenced by the development of

Fig. 7. SEM observation of the coated tensile specimen after loading until 445 MPa / 2100 N (a), (c), (e) and 509 MPa / 2400 N (b), (d), (f).

surface relief and plastic deformation in the underlying metallic substrate.

To trace the complete trajectory of coating fracture progression, the tensile test extended until the ultimate tensile strength reached 658 MPa / 3100 N (step 4), leading to the failure of the specimen (step 5) as depicted in Fig. 8. Notably, from the previous state at 509 MPa (step 3) to 658 MPa (step 4), a substantial plastic elongation of 1140 µm occurred, resulting in the formation of extensive cracks and wide crack

openings (Fig. 8a, c). Fig. 8c shows delamination and sliding cracks with openings varying between 80 to 600 nm. Continuing the tensile test until the specimen's failure highlights a pronounced effect of high elongation, leading to complete delamination of the coating in some areas and complete exposure of the steel (Fig. 8b, d).

Fig. 8. SEM observation of the coated tensile specimen after loading until 658 MPa / 3100 N at unloaded state (a), (c), and after failure (b), (d).

Fig. 9. Oscillation versus number of cycles of VHCF experiments (a), Woehler diagram of (b) coated and uncoated AISI 904L.

3.2. Cyclic loading

In addition to monotonic loading, investigations were also focused on assessing the effect of applied coating on enhancing the fatigue life of

cyclically loaded specimens. To achieve this, VHCF experiments were conducted on both coated and uncoated specimens. The control of oscillation values can be achieved by specifying the test parameters [15], enabling the experiments to be done in displacement control

Fig. 10. Representative fracture surface of VHCF specimens.

mode. In reference to the study conducted by [19], which compared changes in oscillation amplitude between stable and metastable austenitic stainless steels, the conclusion was drawn that the regulation of test parameters during the test is unnecessary for the highly stable AISI 904L. Following this approach, the VHCF tests in this study were conducted without the regulation of test parameters. Fig. 9a illustrates the oscillation value versus the number of cycles for the tested specimens, with uncoated and coated specimens denoted by U and C, respectively. Despite the absence of martensitic phase transformation, a slight increase in oscillation amplitude over time was noticeable in all experiments. This phenomenon can be attributed to the inherent characteristics of austenitic stainless steels, as they are highly soft materials exhibiting elastic–plastic behavior even at low stress amplitudes. This behavior may lead to a slight change in the resonance frequency of the specimen, resulting in a change in oscillation behavior. Despite the observed increase, the oscillation versus number of cycles for all specimens followed a consistent trend, allowing for meaningful comparisons of the results.

To plot the Woehler diagram, the same method outlined in [19] was employed. Following this approach, the oscillation amplitude measured by a laser vibrometer at 10^7 cycles was utilized to recalculate the stress amplitude using the k factor obtained from finite element method (Eq. (1)).

$$\sigma_a(\text{MPa}) = S_a(\mu\text{m}) \times 23.56 (\text{MPa}/\mu\text{m}) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 9b illustrates a noticeable increase in fatigue life for coated specimens, especially at load levels of 340–350 MPa, implying a positive impact of the coating on the fatigue life of AISI 904L. However, this positive effect is relevant only if crack initiation in the specimen occurs from the surface. In VHCF experiments, the specimens did not completely break; instead, they remained partially connected. The crack propagation in these experiments were steady and stable. As the crack initiated on the specimen surface, the specimen continued to oscillate, and crack propagated gradually until the remaining connected area in the cross-section became insufficient for oscillation. This point was considered as the failure point for the specimens. A tensile test was performed on the failed specimens, which were cooled in liquid nitrogen, to disconnect them for fatigue fracture surface analysis. Fig. 10 displays a representative fracture surface of VHCF specimens, where the fatigue crack originated from the surface.

Mechanically polished VHCF specimen has the same topography as the flat tensile specimen, therefore, the coating on the VHCF specimens at initial state exhibits the same appearance as the one on flat tensile specimen, as depicted in Fig. 6a, c. Upon conducting SEM observations on specimens that endured fatigue loading up to 10^9 cycles, no evident fracture in the coating was observed. This suggests that the coating exhibits excellent adhesion to the specimen, as it remained free from decohesion or fracture despite the high-frequency vibrations. Consequently, in order to explore coating fracture resulting from cyclic loading, analyses were performed on specimens after failure. All failed specimens exhibited similar characteristic fractures in the coating; therefore, one exemplar has been chosen for further investigations. Fig. 11a displays the SEM image of the gauge length of the failed specimen that subjected to cyclic loading at 350 MPa and endured 6×10^8 cycles, highlighting the precise locations of the FIB-cut cross sections and Fig. 11b presents a schematic view of the cross-section, detailing its placement on the holder. Upon inspecting the failed specimen surface, no noticeable fractures were detected in the coating away from the macro crack. Observing the macro crack, there was a region with a length of 1.65 mm where no fractures were observed further than a distance of about $10 \mu\text{m}$ from the macro crack in the coating (Fig. 11a). Beyond this region, from both sides, micro cracks and delamination sites began to appear in the coating around the macro crack. However, around the tip of the macro crack, an extensive delamination and further

Fig. 11. SEM image overview accompanied by FIB-cut positions of failed specimen subjected to cyclic loading at 350 MPa and endured 6×10^8 cycles (a), schematic view of the cross-section (b).

Fig. 12. SEM observation of gauge length near the macro crack of cyclically loaded failed specimen (a), (b), and (c).

Fig. 13. CS1, positioned 3.8 mm away from the macro-crack in the specimen, showed no presence of micro-cracks or fractures in the coating.

fractures were observed (Fig. 12a). This observation could be attributed to the fact that by propagation of the crack, the plastic zone around the crack expands and at final stage, the propagation is rather rapid and multi-axial. Fig. 12b, c depict the fracture in vicinity of the macro-crack with a detailed SEM image view of the position of the CS2 and CS3 respectively. In Fig. 12b, in addition to delamination on slip bands, some slip bands can be seen where the coating remained intact and without fracture on top of them. Similarly, Fig. 12c shows plastic deformations in the steel with the coating following the same deformation and staying connected without fracture. However, some areas had sliding cracks and very short elastic cracks. In cyclic loading, the sliding cracks and elastic cracks were not interconnected, and their lengths were significantly shorter than those observed in tensile loading.

To understand the fracture mechanism during cyclic loading, it was worth doing FIB-cut analyses at different positions. The cross section CS1 positioned 3.8 mm away from the macro-crack (Fig. 11a); the coating appeared intact, consistent with the first cross-section image (Fig. 13). As the distance from the middle of the gauge length increases, the specimen experiences a lower stress amplitude. Consequently, this reduced stress amplitude was insufficient to induce any fractures in the coating. Nonetheless, a wavy pattern appeared on the steel surface beneath the coating. The presence of these wavy patterns alongside the

observed linear patterns compared to the specimen's initial state (Fig. 4b) indicates that the material has experienced cyclic loading.

FIB-cut (CS2) was performed approximately 40 μm away from the macro-crack, where delamination of the coating from the steel occurred as a result of the formation of slip bands in the substrate underneath and vibration of the specimen during cyclic loading caused complete decohesion of the coating in that area (Fig. 12b). The comparable delamination size observed in the tensile test was attributed to a significant elongation of approximately 92 μm in the 2nd step by tensile loading. However, during cyclic loading, the material undergoes minimal elongation, typically less than 1 to 5 μm in the gauge length, particularly near the middle of the specimen. In Fig. 14a, on the right side of the CS2, the coating remained attached to the steel. The linear pattern in the steel cross-section under the wavy pattern was more concentrated compared to Fig. 13, suggesting the early stages of persistent slip bands (PSBs) formation. On the left side where the coating was completely detached, there was an elevation in the surface level of the specimen and bigger surface relief.

FIB-cut (CS3) was performed on a sliding micro-crack in the coating (Fig. 12c). The cross-section depicted in Fig. 14b reveals a micro-crack in the coating, followed by the micro-crack in the substrate underneath. Notably, the linear pattern in the substrate appeared more concentrated compared to the second cross-section (Fig. 14a), indicative of the PSBs. On the left side, despite the presence of several PSBs, none of them initiated a crack at the surface, and the wavy pattern did not extend to the steel-coating interface, remaining confined in the nanocrystalline layer region. This could be concluded that the coating suppressed the PSBs and resulted in longer fatigue life compared to uncoated specimens.

4. Conclusions

This study investigates the fracture mechanism of an organically modified silica-based coating, known as EtOH, applied to austenitic stainless steel AISI 904L, under both monotonic and cyclic loading conditions.

In the interrupted monotonic investigations, the following main conclusions and findings emerged:

- Within the macroscopic elastic range for AISI 904L, slip bands emerged after unloading; however, no micro-cracks initiated in the coating. This indicates that, due to significant smaller elastic modulus of the coating (~77 times smaller), the stress developed in the coating during both loading and after unloading, attributed to the presence of slip bands, remained within the elastic regime for the coating. Thus, the macroscopic elastic region for both the steel and the coating was consistent.

Fig. 14. CS2 in vicinity of macro-crack on delamination site and slip bands (a), CS3 in vicinity of macro-crack on a sliding crack in the coating (b).

- Following the emergence of fracture in the coating, micro cracks were observed perpendicular to the loading direction, despite the unique orientation of slip bands in each specific grain. This indicates that under monotonic loading conditions, the emergence of fracture is primarily influenced by the applied elongation, rather than the plastic deformation of the base steel.
- A small FIB-cut with a width of 15 μm and a depth of 10 μm is not sufficient to serve as a stress concentration zone for the steel in monotonic loading. Additionally, this FIB-cut in the thin and soft coating acts as a stress relaxation feature rather than a conventional notch.
- During monotonic loading, three types of fractures were observed: delamination areas, micro-cracks with plastic stress relaxation caused by the sliding of the coating at the metal-coating interface, and micro-cracks with elastic stress relaxation, though their depth had not yet penetrated the entire thickness of the coating. With increasing load steps, other types of fractures eventually transformed into delamination, resulting in the exposure of metal in most areas.

In the VHCF investigations, the following main conclusions and findings emerged:

- The specimens subjected to cyclic loading up to 10^9 cycles did not exhibit any change and fracture in the coating. This observation suggests that the stress amplitude for both the steel and the coating remained within the elastic regime.
- In VHCF experiments, crack initiation occurred from the surface of the specimens. The application of coating improved the surface morphology of the specimens, leading to an increase in fatigue life. This enhancement was demonstrated by performing FIB-cut cross sections and observing that the coating suppressed the persistent slip bands, thereby preventing them from initiating cracks on the surface.
- In the coating after failure, the entire state of fracture in the vicinity of the macro crack in the specimen was comparable to the second step of tensile loading. Interestingly, this similarity persisted despite the limited elongation observed in VHCF within the gauge length of the specimen, reaching a maximum of 1 to 5 μm .

- All fractures observed in the coating during monotonic loading were also visible during cyclic loading, with the distinction that sliding and elastic cracks appeared shorter and were not interconnected. Delamination was notably concentrated very close to the macro crack, within approximately 10 μm on the crack initiation side. Significantly larger delamination was observed at the tip of the macro crack due to the increased size of the plastic zone in front of the macro crack.
- After observing the failed VHCF specimens, it was noted that the fracture and visual changes in the coating were concentrated in the vicinity of the macro crack (10–180 μm depending on the position from crack initiation site). This observation suggests the good adhesion of the coating to the specimen, despite the higher stress amplitude and high-frequency vibrations in the ultrasonic fatigue testing system. However, interrupted tests for the investigation of the origin of micro crack initiation during VHCF loading is required for the future investigations.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Shirin Falakboland: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jolanta Szczurek:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Justyna Krzak:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Grzegorz Lesiuk:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Marek Smaga:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

The research was supported by the National Science Centre, Poland under the OPUS + LAP project 'Research on the influence of self-healing, organic-inorganic sol-gel layers on the corrosion resistance and fatigue of steel in the VHCF range' UMO 2020/39/I/ST5/03493, as well as funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 465237729.

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